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NFDI4Objects
Community Cluster
Research Software
Engineering (RSE)

Geodesist in the Humanities

... working with humanities people on Research Software and FAIRification Tools ...

Florian Thiery M.Sc.

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Session: How to improve the visibility [...] of RSE(s) in NFDI

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14920034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14920034)

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This is me, **Florian Thiery M.Sc.**,
RSE in Task Area 2 “Collecting” within **NFDI4Objects** at LEIZA (Mainz).

Scientific Scripting
Languages in Archaeology
A special interest group of
CAA International dedicated
to scientific scripting
languages in archaeology.

Computer Applications &
Quantitative Methods in Archaeology

In N40 I am closely related to the CAA groups and the Squirrels

My Goal: Open Data with Open Source: FAIR Data with FAIR4RS Tools

The Research Squirrel Engineers Network is a loose association of Linked Open Data/Wikidata enthusiasts, research software engineers and citizen scientists specialising in computational archaeology and geoinformatics.

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+ B. Danthine, A.-K. Distel, Peter Thiery, Fiona Schenk et al.

The members develop and maintain research and FAIRification and FAIRification tools and implement them in specific projects.

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
Research Software
Engineering (RSE)

I am Chair of the N4O Community Cluster RSE
and the WG RSE within the INFRA section in the NFDI e.V.

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
Research Software
Engineering (RSE)

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rse.i | FAIR4RS

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rse.ii | n4o.software

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rse.iii | jupyter4objects

We want to initiate RSE Working Groups

RSE in Action ...

... using the **SPARQL Unicorn Research Toolkit**.

A FAIRification tool for digital data management is the
SPARQL Unicorn and its implementation for QGIS

It contains of

- (i) the **SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin**
- (ii) the **SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation** tool

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph -> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name:

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo WHERE {
2 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <> .
3 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
4 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
5 } LIMIT 10

```


Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

GeometryCollections ClassTree (426)

- taxonomy
- terminology
- thesaurus
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing
- Annotation
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- OghamSite
- OghamStone
- OghamStone_CIIC
- OghamStone_CISP
- OghamStone_O3D
- OghamStone_Squirrel
- Place
 - Place
 - Aufbewahrungsort (Repositor)
 - Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
 - Kiln region (KilnRegion)
 - ProductionCentre
 - Location (Location)
 - Townland
 - Townland
 - geosparql:Feature

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhefter Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFD4Objects Graph -> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: Engl

- GeoConcepts (23)
- AnnotatedThing
 - Barony
 - Barony
 - County
 - County
 - Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
 - GeographicLocation
 - Island
 - Kin region (KinRegion)
 - Location
 - Location (Location)
 - OghamSite**
 - Place
 - ProductionCentre
 - Province
 - State
 - Townland
 - Townland
 - geosparql:Feature
 - sfMultiPolygon
 - sfPoint
 - sfPolygon
 - wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

NFD4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: /api/sparql [see documentation]

Simple view Ellipse Filter query results Page size: All

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
10 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
11 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
12 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Item	label	geo	county	count
1 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000001>	Ballyneock (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.07111 52.026644)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Carik@en	15
2 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000002>	Drumoban (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.668056 52.165056)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Waterford@en	10
3 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000003>	Ballynagart (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(10.03111 52.1732)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
4 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000004>	Kilcolgan East / Kilbullicata (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.74722 52.07144)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
5 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000005>	Knockboy (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.6 52.11189)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Waterford@en	9
6 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000006>	Ballynaring (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(13.06111 52.21611)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
7 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000007>	Coolmagart (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.642778 52.06111)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
8 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000008>	Colbstown / Killeen Cornes (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.756389 53.03111)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Waterford@en	9
9 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000009>	Ballyhans (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.60655 51.83611)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Carik@en	9
10 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000010>	Knockshaneew (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.794722 51.868056)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Carik@en	9
11 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000011>	Whitefield (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.705056 52.08056)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
12 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000012>	Kilgovan (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.549722 52.09056)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Waterford@en	9
13 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000013>	Monatagart (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.779444 51.974444)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Carik@en	9
14 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000014>	Rockfield / Laham (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.631667 52.12889)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Kerry@en	9
15 <http://od.ogham.link/data/O54000015>	Boonee More (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.784167 51.88667)"@geo+VRS:IRIS	Carik@en	9

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8190763](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190763)

This repository hosts a standalone version of the HTML documentation feature included in the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Rather than initiating the documentation generation within the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin, this python script allows the generation of the documentation standalone or as a Github Action.

The standalone script does not rely on QGIS classes and does not provide the full functionality available in the SPARQLUnicorn QGIS Plugin.

Deviations from the SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin are listed as follows:

- Support for less geometry literals: Only WKT and GeoJSON literals are supported for rendering

Usage Example as Github Action

For a usage example please refer to this repository: https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS_testdata

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc>
via 10.5281/zenodo.8190763

HTML creation with the help of Unicorn and GitHub Actions

Breislak, Scipione (1748-1826). Voyages physiques et lythologiques dans la Campanie. Paris: Dentu, Imprimeur-libraire, 1801, via https://vulcan.lindahall.org/12_large.shtml

About 40,000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Evidence of the ash fall from this late Pleistocene volcanic event can be found throughout Central Europe.

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network Nuts?

Site Instances Collection EV

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/Site_collection

The Site Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) ☰

Property	Value
type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	Site Instances Collection (rdf:langString) [iso639:en]
member (dfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▼ 71 values▪ Acerra Sink (fsld:cisite_1)▪ Acqua Fidia (fsld:cisite_2)▪ Baia Alba (Romania) (fsld:cisite_37)▪ Batajnica (fsld:cisite_104)▪ Bratul Borcea (Romania) (fsld:cisite_56)▪ Capezzano (fsld:cisite_3)▪ Casola (fsld:cisite_4)▪ Castelcivita Cave (fsld:cisite_5)▪ Copecchia (fsld:cisite_6)

All these sites and information can be visualised via the Unicorn

Using **Python Minions** these data could be also transformed into **QuickStatements** within the **fuzzy-sl Wikibase**

Auel Maar (AU3/4) & Dehner Maar (DE3) sites in Schenk et al. (2024)

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q70>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools

What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase

New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Auel Maar AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site	▼ 0 references
related to	https://kulturb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch	▼ 0 references
has reference	Schenk et al. (2024)	► 1 reference
part of	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots	▼ 0 references
has spatial type	Maar	▼ 0 references

has coordinate 50°16'57.0"N, 6°35'42.4"E

certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place

▼ 1 reference

reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017
---------------	---

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU3 [Q70] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Jupyter Python Minions as Jupyter Notebooks

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q8016167.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

Map 3: Density map with normalized values

```
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y
```

Calculate kernel density

```
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)
```

Normalize density to range [0, 1]

```
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized
```

```
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query for Samian Ware Kiln Sites
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
  ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
  ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
  ?c a oghamonto:County .
  ?c rdfs:label ?county .
  ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
  ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```


Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "county": result.get("county", {}).get("value", None),
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0))
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


	county	count
0	Kerry	127
1	Cork	81
2	Waterford	47
3	Kilkenny	12
4	Kildare	8
5	Mayo	8
6	Wexford	5
7	Wicklow	5
8	Carlow	4
9	Clare	3
10	Limerick	3
11	Roscommon	3
12	Antrim	2
13	Cavan	2
14	Meath	2
15	Tipperary	2

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Pie Chart

```
# Calculate the total number of stones.
total_count = df["count"].sum()

# Compute the percentage for each county.
df["percentage"] = df["count"] / total_count * 100

# Separate counties with a percentage >= 3% from those with less than 3%.
major_df = df[df["percentage"] >= 3].copy()
minor_df = df[df["percentage"] < 3].copy()

# If there are counties with less than 3%, combine them into an 'Other' category.
if not minor_df.empty:
    other_count = minor_df["count"].sum()
    major_df = pd.concat([major_df, pd.DataFrame({"county": "Other", "count": other_count})], ignore_index=True)

# Optional: Sort the categories by count in descending order.
major_df = major_df.sort_values("count", ascending=False)

# Define a function to format the autopct text to include both the percentage and the stone count.
def make_autopct(values):
    def my_autopct(pct):
        total = sum(values)
        count = int(round(pct * total / 100.0))
        return '{:.1f}% ({:d})'.format(pct, count)
    return my_autopct

# Create a pie chart displaying the distribution of OghamSites by county.
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))
major_df.set_index("county")["count"].plot(
    kind="pie",
    autopct=make_autopct(major_df["count"]),
    startangle=90,
    colors=plt.cm.Paired.colors
)
plt.title("Distribution of OghamSites by County (Categories <3% grouped as 'Other')", fontsize=16)
plt.ylabel("") # Remove the default y-label.
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Scatter Plot

```
# Create a scatter plot with county on the x-axis and stone count on the y-axis.
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
x_positions = range(len(df))
plt.scatter(x_positions, df["count"], color="blue")
plt.title("Scatter Plot: Stone Count per County", fontsize=16)
plt.xlabel("County", fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel("Stone Count", fontsize=14)

# Create customised x-axis labels with county and count in square brackets.
xtick_labels = [f"{{county}} [{{count}}]" for county, count in zip(df["county"], df["count"])]
plt.xticks(x_positions, xtick_labels, rotation=45, ha="right")

# Add a light grey grid.
plt.grid(color="lightgrey", linestyle="--", linewidth=0.5)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Create Charts

Distribution of OghamSites by County (Categories <3% grouped as 'Other')

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np
```

```
def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

```
# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
  ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
  ?item rdfs:label ?label .
  ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
  ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
  ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
  ?c a oghamonto:County .
  ?c rdfs:label ?county .
  ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
  ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062	Castletimon (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.909167	-6.063611
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168	Knickeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.998056	-6.535000
193	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000045	Boleycarrigeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.947012	-6.608898
194	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000098	Donard (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	53.016944	-6.617778
195	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000040	Baltinglass (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.966389	-6.624444

196 rows x 6 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()
# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count

```
# Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count.
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
# Extract x and y coordinates from the GeoDataFrame.
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Define a scaling factor for point sizes.
size_factor = 10
sizes = gdf_mercator["count"] * size_factor

# Plot the points using a continuous colormap (e.g. 'viridis') based on the stone count.
sc = ax.scatter(x, y, s=sizes, c=gdf_mercator["count"], cmap="viridis", alpha=0.7, edgecolor="k")
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count", fontsize=16)

# Add a colour bar with label.
cbar = plt.colorbar(sc, ax=ax)
cbar.set_label("Stone Count", fontsize=12)
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

- Counties
- Cork
 - Waterford
 - Kerry
 - Kildare
 - Antrim
 - Kilkenny
 - Roscommon
 - Armagh
 - Carlow
 - Cavan
 - Clare
 - Donegal
 - Dublin
 - Fermanagh
 - Galway
 - Leitrim
 - Limerick
 - Londonderry
 - Louth
 - Mayo
 - Meath
 - Tipperary
 - Tyrone
 - Wexford
 - Wicklow

Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count

Output

Finis! Thx!

Questions?

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